

High-resolution free-breathing automated quantitative myocardial perfusion by cardiovascular magnetic resonance for the detection of functionally significant coronary artery disease

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Aims

Current assessment of myocardial ischaemia from stress perfusion cardiovascular magnetic resonance (SP-CMR) largely relies on visual interpretation. This study investigated the use of high-resolution free-breathing SP-CMR with automated quantitative mapping in the diagnosis of coronary artery disease (CAD). Diagnostic performance was evaluated against invasive coronary angiography (ICA) with fractional flow reserve (FFR) measurement.

Methods and results

Seven hundred and three patients were recruited for SP-CMR using the research sequence at 3 Tesla. Of those receiving ICA within 6 months, 80 patients had either FFR measurement or identification of a chronic total occlusion (CTO) with inducible perfusion defects seen on SP-CMR. Myocardial blood flow (MBF) maps were automatically generated in-line on the scanner following image acquisition at hyperaemic stress and rest, allowing myocardial perfusion reserve (MPR) calculation. Seventy-five coronary vessels assessed by FFR and 28 vessels with CTO were evaluated at both segmental and coronary territory level. Coronary territory stress MBF and MPR were reduced in FFR-positive (≤ 0.80) regions [median stress MBF: 1.74 (0.90–2.17) mL/min/g; MPR: 1.67 (1.10–1.89)] compared with FFR-negative regions [stress MBF: 2.50 (2.15–2.95) mL/min/g; MPR 2.35 (2.06–2.54) $P < 0.001$ for both]. Stress MBF ≤ 1.94 mL/min/g and MPR ≤ 1.97 accurately detected FFR-positive CAD on a per-vessel basis (area under the curve: 0.85 and 0.96, respectively; $P < 0.001$ for both).

Conclusion

A novel scanner-integrated high-resolution free-breathing SP-CMR sequence with automated in-line perfusion mapping is presented which accurately detects functionally significant CAD.

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Figure 1 Contrast transit over time during sequence acquisition in a patient with normal MBF. Row (A) represents AIF slice acquisition over time and row (B) demonstrates the basal myocardial slice at the same time points. (C) Automated segmentation of the AIF longitudinal relaxation rate (R1) map series used as a region of interest (ROI) for assessment of the AIF. (D) Basal myocardial R1 series with an ROI placed in the interventricular septum. (E) Time-R1 curves of both the automated AIF ROI and manual ROI seen in the R1 series.

The aim of this study was to establish the diagnostic accuracy of this high-resolution automated quantitative perfusion mapping pipeline to identify functionally significant CAD in clinical patients. The accuracy of the sequence was evaluated by comparison of the automatically generated MBF values with corresponding ICA findings and FFR measurements.

Methods

Study population

Patients aged 18–90 were prospectively recruited between January 2022 and May 2023 at St Thomas' Hospital, London, UK. The patients were referred for investigation of CAD by SP-CMR based on the reported symptoms. All provided written consent as part of a large cohort observational study, with ethical approval provided by the North of Scotland Research Ethics Committee (ref. 15/NS/0030). All participants underwent high-resolution SP-CMR with in-line quantitative mapping visible to the reporting clinicians. Participants were included for analysis if they underwent ICA (performed by the patient's clinical team) within 6 months of their SP-CMR scan (before or after); patients were excluded in the event of change in anti-anginal

medication, myocardial infarction, or coronary revascularization within this timeframe. Patients receiving clinically indicated FFR evaluation in one or more coronary arteries were included in the 'FFR' study subgroup. Patients with an occlusion within the proximal-to-mid portions of a major epicardial coronary artery, along with the visual identification of an inducible perfusion defect in the same territory (exceeding the boundaries of any infarction scarring seen on late gadolinium-enhanced imaging), were included within the 'chronic total occlusion (CTO)' study subgroup. Patients were excluded from this subgroup if there was evidence of transmural/near-transmural infarction scarring within the territory.

Perfusion image acquisition

All patients underwent SP-CMR on a single 3T scanner (MAGNETOM Vida, Siemens Healthineers AG, Erlangen, Germany) with an 18-channel flexible phased array coil and 72-channel spine coil array. Subjects were asked to abstain from nicotine and caffeinated products for 24 h prior to the SP-CMR scan. Perfusion imaging consisted of 60–70 dynamic acquisitions using a saturation recovery fast gradient echo research sequence in free breathing. A bolus of 0.075 mmol/kg gadobutrol (Gadovist, Bayer AG, Leverkusen, Germany) was administered at 4 mL/s with 20 mL saline flush

Table 1 Baseline characteristics at the time of CMR scan

	FFR group (n = 60)	CTO group (n = 20)
Age	61.5 (56.0–71.0)	62.0 (55.5–70.5)
Sex		
Male	31 (51.7)	13 (65.0)
Stress agent		
Adenosine	56 (93.3)	19 (95.0)
Left ventricular ejection fraction	59.0 (55.0–64.0)	47.0 (39.5–58.0)
Cardiac rhythm		
Sinus rhythm	58 (96.7)	20 (100.0)
Atrial fibrillation	2 (3.3)	0 (0.0)
History of CAD	24 (40.0)	14 (70.0)
Previous coronary intervention		
None	48 (80.0)	11 (55.0)
PCI	11 (18.3)	6 (30.0)
CABG	1 (1.7)	3 (15.0)
Diabetes mellitus	19 (31.7)	13 (65.0)
Hypercholesterolaemia	40 (66.7)	11 (55.0)
Hypertension	34 (56.7)	16 (80.0)
Smoking history		
None	36 (60.0)	8 (40.0)
Ex-smoker	20 (33.3)	12 (60.0)
Current smoker	4 (6.7)	0 (0.0)
Presence of LGE (any myocardial segment)	22 (36.7)	18 (90.0)
Visual interpretation of perfusion defect		
Regional hypo-perfusion	10 (16.7)	20 (100.0)
No regional hypo-perfusion	50 (83.3) ^a	0 (0.0)

Continuous variables displayed as median (inter-quartile range); discrete variables displayed as frequency (group %).

PCI, percutaneous coronary intervention; CABG, coronary artery bypass grafting.

^aFour patients within this group had a poor response to vasodilator and were not included in analysis.

if the sampling points bridged multiple pixels. Segmental MBF was calculated as the mean of the MBF values of the sampling points within each AHA segment. Myocardial perfusion reserve (MPR) for each AHA segment was calculated as the ratio of mean segmental MBF at hyperaemia (stress MBF) and mean segmental MBF during resting conditions (rest MBF). An estimation of total coronary territorial perfusion was calculated as the mean of the corresponding segmental MBF and MPR values in AHA segments traditionally associated with each coronary territory.³³ Segmental and territorial perfusion values were extracted and organized using Python code. To allow comparison with previous studies, the mean of the two lowest scoring stress MBF values from AHA segments within each coronary territory were also considered ('lowest 2 segment' method).^{16,17} The corresponding MPR was calculated using the mean segmental MPR values from these same segments at rest.

Statistical analysis

Analysis was conducted using SPSS Statistics version 29 (IBM, Armonk, NY, USA). Shapiro–Wilk testing demonstrated that segmental and territorial

stress and rest MBF values were not normally distributed amongst the population. As such, continuous variables are represented as median (inter-quartile range), whilst categorical variables are represented as frequencies and corresponding percentage. Correlation of non-parametric continuous variables was evaluated by the Spearman correlation coefficient. The comparison of statistical significance among multiple categorical groups was conducted using a Mann–Whitney *U* test for two categories, and Kruskal–Wallis testing for more than two categories. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) analysis was used to assess the diagnostic accuracy of quantitative datasets. Calculation of both sensitivity and specificity was established using a Youden index to identify optimal cut-offs for both stress MBF and MPR. Area under the curve (AUC) values is represented alongside asymptotic 95% confidence intervals. McNemar's test was used to compare sensitivity and specificity of different analysis methods. Significance was assessed via two-sided testing and a *P*-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. All graphs and plots were generated directly from the data via Python code.

Results

Seven hundred and three patients receiving SP-CMR were recruited in total. Two hundred and eight recruited patients had invasive angiography within 6 months of their clinical SP-CMR investigations. Of these, 60 patients had pressure wire-guided FFR assessment performed, and another 20 patients were identified as having an inducible perfusion defect in the same coronary territory as an epicardial CTO. Only these patients were selected for analysis. The baseline characteristics for each group are shown in Table 1. Ten FFR measurements were assessed as abnormal and functionally significant, as defined by FFR value ≤ 0.80 . All other FFR measurements were >0.80 , and therefore deemed to be not functionally significant, irrespective of the presence of visually identified lesions on the ICA.

Four patients who received both invasive FFR and SP-CMR were excluded from the quantitative analysis due to poor hyperaemic response to the vasodilator during the SP-CMR. Reasons for poor hyperaemic response included consumption of caffeine or nicotine products prior to the scan, or ineffectual/under-estimation of vasodilator administration. Stress perfusion values were analysed without MPR calculation in nine patients—the reasons for this included rest perfusion imaging not being performed, the use of regadenoson as vasodilatory agent, and the identification of significant artefact within the rest perfusion map.

Qualitative visual assessment of the myocardial perfusion series (both with and without motion compensation) was performed for all the included patients. Ten patients were adjudged to have regional hypo-perfusion defects. Seven of these were found to have one or more FFR-positive lesions via ICA. The remaining three patients were found to have FFR >0.80 in the presumed ischaemic coronary territories. Additionally, one patient with no evidence of regional hypo-perfusion on visual assessment was found to have a single positive coronary territory on FFR assessment.

Relationship between FFR and territorial CMR quantitative perfusion values

In total, 75 global coronary artery FFR measurements were matched to the corresponding coronary territorial MBF values obtained at peak hyperaemic stress. Where rest imaging was included in analysis, a total of 63 territorial FFR-to-MPR values were obtained. Examples of automated maps from these patients are shown in Figure 3. In two patients, the apical AHA segments were not included in calculating the mean territorial perfusion values due to artefact within the extrapolated maps at peak stress.

Figure 4 Comparison of perfusion values from whole territory and lowest two AHA segments analysis methods: (A) stress MBF and (B) MPR. Both stress MBF and MPR were lower in FFR-positive territories, regardless of the method used for assessment.

the higher prevalence of LGE scarring seen within this cohort. An example case is demonstrated in *Figure 7*.

The median stress MBF in patients with CTO and inducible ischaemia was 1.31 (1.11–1.56) mL/min/g; rest MBF was 1.02 (0.85–1.27) mL/min/g; and MPR was 1.24 (1.01–1.46). When analysed alongside the FFR patient cohort, there was a clear trend in stress MBF and MPR values across all ischaemic categories (CTO with inducible defect, FFR ≤ 0.80, FFR 0.81–0.90, FFR > 0.90; $P < 0.001$ for both stress MBF and MPR) (*Figure 8*). When considering group-wise comparison, both stress MBF and MPR were significantly lower in CTO territories compared with both FFR-negative groups (all $P < 0.001$), but no significant difference was seen compared with the FFR-positive group (stress MBF, $P = 0.140$; MPR, $P = 0.259$).

Discussion

This study demonstrates that the presented high-resolution free-breathing perfusion sequence with in-line automated quantitative mapping can be used to accurately detect functionally significant epicardial CAD (as defined as FFR ≤ 0.80). These findings are comparable to other automated SP-CMR quantitative mapping techniques.^{20,34} The proposed framework uses the Fermi deconvolution method which has been well validated against quantitative cardiac positron-emission tomography, invasive FFR and microsphere evaluation.^{17,35,36} Furthermore, this is the first time that automated quantitative perfusion mapping has been combined with high-resolution perfusion imaging and respiratory motion compensation, all implemented within the scanner

Figure 6 ROC curves assessing the effectiveness of quantitative perfusion map analysis in identification of functionally significant CAD (as defined by FFR \leq 0.80) on a per-vessel level. Each curve represents a different analysis approach with both stress MBF and MPR shown. (A) Whole territory perfusion values. (B) Mean of lowest two AHA segment perfusion values.

Figure 7 A patient with CTO and inducible perfusion defect included in analysis. (A) Stress MBF maps with a defect seen in the LAD artery territory (mean MBF 1.70 mL/min/g vs. 2.35 mL/min/g in the other territories). (B) Dark-blood LGE imaging demonstrating sub-endocardial infarction in the LAD territory, smaller in distribution than the perfusion defect seen in (A). ICA demonstrated a CTO in the LAD with collaterals from the circumflex artery.

methods for stress MBF. Despite this, the AUC for MPR was lower for the lowest two-segment method, suggesting a better performance of whole territory MPR analysis.

The addition of the patients with CTO and associated inducible perfusion defect helped to emphasize a clear trend in perfusion values across ischaemic categories, with perfusion values (both stress MBF

and MPR) significantly reduced in those with presumed severe ischaemia. However, with no invasive FFR measurement in these patients possible, these patients could not be included the ROC analysis for diagnostic accuracy.

With recent large clinical trials highlighting the importance of optimal medical management in many patients with CAD, non-invasive

Figure 8 Perfusion values across ischaemic categories (defined by invasive coronary assessment). Both stress MBF (A) and MPR (B) values were significantly lower in FFR-positive and CTO categories compared with FFR-negative categories. Whole group analysis showed increased perfusion values across ischaemic categories ($P < 0.001$). No significant difference was seen between both FFR-negative categories (both stress MBF and MPR).

functional imaging is important in deciding the best management strategy for patients.^{37,38} With FFR-guided revascularization known to improve long-term outcomes, the accurate identification of functionally significant lesions from fully automated quantitative SP-CMR would allow clinicians to make individual management decisions from non-invasive imaging.³⁹ With wider availability and good diagnostic accuracy, there is the potential for quantitative SP-CMR to augment both the diagnosis and management of myocardial ischaemia in CAD, without the need for direct visualization of the coronary arteries.

High-resolution quantitative perfusion maps

The diagnostic accuracy of both stress MBF and MPR in predicting functionally significant CAD in this study may, in part, be due to the high-spatial resolution of the perfusion sequence and its derived quantitative mapping. Higher spatial resolution is likely to be advantageous in visual interpretation of images and perfusion maps with clearer identification of perfusion defects and a decreased impact of dark-rim artefact within the myocardial images.¹⁰ This study did not assess the specific

advantages of high-resolution quantitative perfusion mapping—although the improved spatial resolution may allow more accurate assessment of transmural perfusion gradients, particularly in the context of myocardial infarction, where judging peri-infarction ischaemia can be difficult.

The continuing importance of rest perfusion imaging and MPR

In this study, MPR appeared to perform better than stress MBF with regard to the sensitivity of detecting FFR-positive CAD. In a small number of patients, though, rest imaging was not acquired, most commonly due to poor baseline renal function. Recent protocol guidelines have suggested a diminished usefulness of rest imaging in diagnosing CAD and that rest perfusion sequences could be omitted from standard SP-CMR protocols.⁴⁰ However, multiple factors may have an effect on MBF at both rest and during hyperaemia, including sex, left ventricular systolic function, and cardiac rhythm.^{41,42} Without a unifying method for correcting stress MBF for these factors, and with the good sensitivity and specificity demonstrated in this study, MPR may represent a more robust assessment of myocardial perfusion in patients with MBF values outside of typical ranges.

Limitations of this study

As an observational study, there was no control over the number of patients referred for ICA and pressure wire-guided FFR measurements—management decisions were independently made by patients' clinical care teams. With growing understanding of the findings from the CE-MARC2 and MR-INFORM trials in predicting the outcome and risk of CAD, fewer patients received FFR assessment during ICA than anticipated prior to revascularization.^{6,9}

With a smaller number of patients with FFR measurements ≤ 0.80 included in the analysis compared with FFR-negative vessels, the calculated sensitivity of automated stress MBF in predicting FFR-positive lesions may be underestimated. The inclusion of the patients from the CTO subgroup would likely have increased the calculated sensitivity—though this would have assumed that all vessels within this subgroup were FFR-positive, without a valid invasive comparison. Instead, the CTO subgroup analysis was included to help balance the study cohort by demonstrating the use of the sequence in those patients with severe ischaemia. Severe ischaemia was not well represented in the FFR subgroup, with the majority of FFR-positive measurements between 0.70 and 0.80.

The analysis in this study was based on the standard coronary territories from the AHA 17-segment model and was not altered based on findings from a patient's ICA.³³ This ensured standardization across all patients in a bid to reduce bias. However, the stress MBF and MPR measurements within some coronary territories may be underestimated, particularly if perfusion defects straddled multiple AHA coronary territories.

Finally, the use of rate-pressure product (RPP) to correct rest MBF and MPR values was not included in the analysis. In theory, this could result in the under-estimation of perfusion reserve in those with hypertension. However, neither resting systolic blood pressure nor RPP correlated with rest MBF values in this cohort.

Conclusions

This novel high-resolution free-breathing perfusion sequence with automated in-line quantitative mapping can accurately detect and rule out the presence of CAD. With SP-CMR being increasingly used in the diagnosis and risk stratification of patients, adoption of this technique provides a robust assessment of MBF and perfusion reserve.

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Conflict of interest: As well as their research roles at King's College London, K.P.K. and S.M. are employed as part of Magnetic Resonance Research Collaborations within Siemens Healthcare Limited. All other authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

Data availability

The data underlying this article will be shared upon reasonable request to the corresponding author.

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